

1 **The islet cell antigen ICA1 marks the terminal ileum in Crohn's Disease.**

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7 Inflammatory bowel disease is a hematopoietic-derived disease whose major pathologic consequence is
8 found in the gastrointestinal tract. Stem cell transplant can resolve disease activity in the GI tract in cases
9 of severe, treatment resistant IBD, supporting a hematopoietic cell of origin in Crohn's Disease (CD).
10 Pathologic function of genes conferring genetic risk of IBD, like NOD2, results in IBD in humans. Variation
11 in NOD2 is also significantly correlated with transplant outcome after stem cell transplant in humans with
12 blood cancer as well as the development of graft versus host disease following HSCT, indicating NOD2
13 has functions in transplant biology with relevance to colitis arising during acute rejection or GVHD.

14 Here, we measured total transcription in the terminal ileum in healthy control individuals and in humans
15 with Crohn's Disease to identify genes whose expression define the terminal ileum in CD

16 We report identification of a molecule known to be perturbed in autoimmune disease, with functions that
17 in self non-self discrimination, *ICA1*, as a significant component of the CD gene signature in the GI tract.
18 *ICA1* expression specifically demarcated the terminal ileum in humans indicating its likely involvement in
19 disease restricted to the terminal ileum in humans with CD.
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Results

It is likely that some abnormal interaction between tissues of the GI tract and/or change in function (gain or loss of function) associated with expression of the variant in the blood but affecting the GI tract is a source of but specific molecular mechanisms that precisely describe a set of events beginning with expression of the mutant alleles in the blood and commencing in inflammatory, obstructive (structuring) and penetrating disease in the GI tract has not yet been described.

We recently described control of genes encoded by the lymphocyte antigen (Ly) family as a major biologic function of NOD2, Ly antigen as a major component of the transplant tolerance gene signature, evidenced by enhanced or silenced expression of multiple Ly antigens in the blood and in the tissues in humans with acute rejection of following solid organ transplant and in humans with chronic graft versus host disease following HSCT.

Together with demonstration that control of Ly antigen expression by wild-type human NOD2 is significantly altered in cells expressing mutant NOD2, the data suggested a major functional role for Ly antigens in immunologic tolerance evident by transcriptome profiling acute rejection, and a tolerogenic function for the innate immune receptor NOD2 that functioned at least in part through control of Ly antigen expression.

The terminal ileum is the most common site of disease in humans with Crohn's Disease. We measured total transcription in the terminal ileum in healthy control individuals and in humans with Crohn's Disease to identify genes whose expression define the terminal ileum in CD

Figure 1: Identification a molecule known to be perturbed in autoimmune disease with functions that also functions in self non-self discrimination, ICA1, as a significant component of the CD gene signature in the GI tract

Altered expression of ICA1 is described in humans with a separate autoimmune disease, in the islet cells of the pancreas in humans with type I diabetes.

ICA1 was activated while ICA1L expression is significantly reduced

Figure 2: Expression of a second self antigen, transplantation antigen TSTA3 is activated in the TI in humans with CD.

Figure 3: Ly family antigens were modulated in the terminal ileum including Ly9 and Ly6g6c.

Figure 4: Rhesus blood group CcEe antigen was activated while Rhesus antigen D was repressed

We undertook a systems biological approach to discovering biologic contexts most significantly associated with ICA1 expression or changes in ICA1 expression.

We identified tissue specific expression of ICA1 in the gastrointestinal tract in normal, healthy humans.

Figure 5: ICA1 is expressed throughout the GI tract but in the terminal ileum ICA1 expression is reduced or absent.

1 **Discussion**

2 Multiple models have been suggested that each aim to describe the molecular mechanism by which
3 humans develop inflammatory bowel disease since discovery of NOD2 as the gene encoded by IBD,
4 including TLR receptor propagated and disease resulting from or largely caused by IL-1B dysruption or
changes in Th17 signaling.

5 Together we provide further evidence indicating that a natural killer-mediated process involving Ly antigen
6 expression (or process that utilizes the Ly antigen based immunologic interface resembling that utilized by
the NK cell in self non-self discrimination)

7 It is likely that a severe disruption in immunologic tolerance at the epithelial barrier of the GI tract involving
8 the pathogen sensing function of the innate immune receptor NOD2, control of Ly antigen expression in
9 the blood by NOD2, contribution of soluble effectors that normally maintain tolerogenic and homeostatic
conditions that are also a property of NOD2 result in an aberrant self non-self reaction originating in the
terminal ileum.

10 Granuloma formation in the terminal ileum indicates that macrophages are recruited and become
functionally associated; this likely occurs subsequent to an initial break in tolerance.

11 Rather than ICA1 expression a reflection of inflammatory gene expression following induction of disease I,
12 ICA1 induction likely precedes and is a contributor of (rather than reflection of) the break in tolerance and
induction of inflammation that results in terminal ileum-specific disease in humans with IBD

13 Further study of events with enhanced chronologic detail during the natural course of disease that
14 demonstrates without doubt how genetic variation results in a blood cell specific defect that subsequently
results in tissue and location-specific inflammatory pathology.

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Methods

We used whole transcriptome technologies and published or public datasets for this study (GSE20881 and GDS3268).